

Windbreaks: Structure and Functionality

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Windbreaks create important habitats and shelter for wild animals

Windbreaks belong to agroforestry systems, whose primary function is to reduce wind erosion on large agricultural plots. They can also serve as a shield against snow drifts or as habitats for wild animals. In addition to the original soil protection function of windbreaks, their landscape-forming function is currently increasingly emphasized. Researchers from the Mendel University (Czech Republic) and National Forest Centre (Slovakia) analyzed the conditions and functionality of the windbreaks in the southeast part of the Czech Republic in the cadastral area of Hrušky village. Most windbreaks were established in the 1960s with a diverse range of tree species. The detected width of windbreaks ranged from 7 to 39 m. Common oak prevailed in the tree composition of analyzed windbreak with 35 %, followed by maple ash (22 %) and black poplar (16 %). There was also a lower proportion of field elm (12 %), black walnut (8 %) and small-leaved linden (6 %). The height of the windbreak depended on the tree composition and ranged from 2 to 31.5 m; the upper storey often consisted of black poplar, under which other tree species were applied. The functionality and health conditions of the windbreak were very variable. Windbreaks despite the worsened health conditions and lack of stand care, their primary function can be expected to be fulfilled. Nevertheless, it is advisable to recommend tree densities and species composition regulation by thinning intervention specified for concrete segments. Partial or complete reconstructions can be recommended in the places with unsatisfactory tree structure component.

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